

Analysis of Collaborative Selection in the Implementation of Finnish Positive Learning in the Ciputra School Network

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ABSTRACT: Education is a crucial aspect of life because it relates to the socialization of values and the development of individual abilities. Global values are also constantly evolving, and each country competes to build and improve its education system. It's no surprise, then, that services in the field of education are now a commodity in the global market. Finland is currently renowned as one of the countries with the best education systems in the world. This is because the curriculum promoted by the Finnish government focuses on character development, well-being, equality, and the social and creative development of students. In Indonesia, several schools have partnered with Finnish educational agencies, particularly the Finnish National Agency for Education, to incorporate aspects of Positive Learning into their school curriculum. This is because Positive Learning is generally superior and effective when applied to lower grades. However, the Ciputra school network is collaborating to develop Positive Learning for implementation in upper grades. Therefore, for this reason, this study employs social capital theory to analyze the relationship between Finnish educational agents and Ciputra schools in Indonesia, as well as the collaborative practices and implementation of Positive Learning in schools, drawing on Pierre Bourdieu's cultural capital theory. This study uses a qualitative approach to data processing. This study aims to determine the school's objectives for implementing Finnish Positive Learning. The question is, "Why did Ciputra schools choose to use Positive Learning in Education Finland as character education for the Upper Grade level?"

KEYWORDS: Positive Learning, School, Curriculum, Indonesia, Finland

I. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary society is characterized by the diminishing significance of national barriers across economic, political, social, and cultural domains. Globalization facilitates connections among individuals worldwide, influencing social interactions at both local levels, such as within families and communities, and broader levels, including among cultures, religions, professions, and nations.¹ The increasing globalization of all aspects of life, particularly education, is driven by ongoing technological and informational advancements that exert reciprocal influence.

The process of globalization is causing the boundaries between countries and individuals to blur, and in this case, global interaction occurs not only at the national level but also at the individual level. Therefore, there is a need for global values that are considered universal, namely equality and humanitarian values. In terms of interaction, both in daily life and in the workplace, the importance of character that can adapt within a global scope is essential. As a result, countries around the world are striving to improve and align the quality of their education with global standards. Countries with a good reputation for education today are also contributing to shaping and building education in less developed countries. One such country with a good reputation in the world today, according to PISA, is Finland.

The Finnish government has created a cluster program called Education Finland. Education in Finland is essentially supported by the government. Its goal is to become a provider of Finnish educational services and products in the global market. Finland considers education a commodity in the global market because its education system is widely regarded as one of the best in the world. The Education Finland program is coordinated by the Finnish National Agency for Education in collaboration with the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, the Finnish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the Private Sector.² Education Finland

¹ Cholil, A. F. (2019). PENGARUH GLOBALISASI DAN ERA DISRUPSI TERHADAP PENDIDIKAN DAN NILAI-NILAI KEISLAMAN . SUKMA: JURNAL PENDIDIKAN, 117-137.

² Agency for Education, F. N., & Finland, E. (2020, June 1). Learning Together. Retrieved from Education Finland: https://www.educationfinland.fi/sites/default/files/2020-06/EducationFinland_LearningTogether_2020_0.pdf

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enables the Finnish government to establish global education partnerships by offering teacher training, curriculum development, and educational reforms grounded in the Finnish education system.

Positive Learning is a learning method that aligns with Finnish culture. Finland emphasizes an egalitarian education, where every student is treated equally and values are shared universally. Finnish education, marketed globally, emphasizes creating a comfortable school environment for student development by encouraging teachers to view students positively and recognize each student's potential. Thus, this potential can be further developed by teachers according to the values and social skills that form the basis of Positive Learning.

The integration of Positive Learning principles into general education fosters the development of student capabilities. The Education Finland program advances this objective by emphasizing both student growth and comprehensive teacher training. Multiple Indonesian schools have established collaborations with Finnish education agencies to implement Positive Learning as a core component of character education initiatives.

In Indonesia, one of the schools that collaborates to implement Positive Learning is the network of schools under the Ciputra Group. According to the School General Manager of Sekolah Citra Kasih, Boedi Tjusila, students need happiness (well-being) to discover their strengths and talents from a young age to support a better future. Finland, with its high level of happiness among students and teachers, is recognized as having the best education system in the world. He said that his school has a concept of Positive Learning, which is one of the unique features of their educational approach. Boedi explained that his school adopts the Positive Education program from Finland, a country with a high level of well-being, to ensure that students have the best possible chance of success in life.³ Based on the previous explanation, this research is formulated as the question: Why does Ciputra School choose to use Positive Learning from Education Finland as its character education approach?

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research examines the relationship between school institutions in Indonesia that choose to implement Positive Learning, a component of educational products provided by the Finnish government. From the perspective of education and culture in international relations, this involves the realization of the concept of soft power. In behavioral terms, soft power is an attractive force, while in terms of resources, the sources of soft power are assets that create appeal.⁴ In this case, Ciputra School in Indonesia is influenced by the excellence of Finnish education and implements it in its institution. The explanation of the influence of Finnish soft power can be elucidated within the theoretical framework of Pierre Bourdieu's concepts of social and cultural capital, considering that Finnish education can attract other countries to adopt Finnish values and teaching methods in their institutions, particularly in Indonesia.

Bourdieu's theory of social structure is a dialectical relationship between individuals or actors (agents, subjective structures) and the objective structure, namely the structure itself. This dialectical relationship involves subjective elements, such as individual mental states and experiential structures, as well as cognitive structures, which interact with the objective structure. This dialectic produces "practice." Within this dialectical relationship, Bourdieu developed concepts to explain these "subjective" and "objective" structures, namely, what he called "habitus" and "field."

Research Variable Table

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable
Habitus: the behavior exhibited by both Finnish educational institutions in marketing their educational products and by schools in Indonesia that aim to develop their learning curriculum in line with the school's vision and mission.	Capital: The material and non-material abilities possessed by individuals or institutions that can be used to compete in the field. Capital will influence the habitus in maintaining or changing its position within the social structure. Capital also influences the habitus among individuals as well as institutions in their interactions.
	Field: The arena is a place where individuals and institutions compete to gain status and power.

(source: Author summary)

³ Zubaidah, N. (2022, Desember 7). Sekolah Citra Kasih Terapkan Positive Learning untuk Kebahagiaan Siswa dan Guru. Retrieved from Sindo News: <https://edukasi.sindonews.com/read/962593/212/sekolah-citra-kasih-terapkan-positive-learning-untuk-kebahagiaan-siswa-dan-guru-1670397121>

⁴ Kristiana, C., & Benito, R. (2023). Implementasi Diplomasi Pendidikan dan Diplomasi. Indonesian Perspective, 121-153.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research employs a qualitative method, utilizing secondary data, conducted deductively. The data will be analyzed based on Pierre Bourdieu's Social Structure theory, examining the interaction between institutions and the state within the international system of cooperation, which can occur when supported by capital, habitus, and field.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Ciputra School's Perspective on Viewing Finland's Symbolic Capital as One of the Global Standards

Finland is one of the countries with the strongest performance in the world in children's literacy and mathematics skills. The country has recently overhauled its education system, and the World Economic Forum now ranks it among the best in the world. The government has eliminated standard tests to avoid forcing students to constantly study for exams instead of actually learning. Instead, children in Finland are assessed individually and through a system created by their teachers. Tracking is carried out by the Ministry of Education. Students in Finland start their day later because research indicates that starting earlier is detrimental to students' health and learning. School begins at the age of seven, allowing children to be children – an attitude that also applies to homework, which is far less compared to other countries. However, students in Finland perform better than those in education systems with longer school hours. Parents can spend more time with their children and also develop close relationships with teachers.⁵

B. Ciputra School's Perspective on the Cultural Capital Held by Finland in the Field of Education

The Finnish education system demonstrates a strong commitment to educational equality. All students are entitled to high-quality education, and national standardized examinations that rank schools or students are not implemented. The system emphasizes individual student development and aims to support each learner in achieving their academic potential without imposing excessive performance pressure.

In addition, practical and creative education plays an important role in learning. They integrate academic learning with practical activities, such as arts, music, sports, and crafts. This helps promote critical thinking skills, creativity, and problem-solving among students, while also providing them with opportunities to develop their interests and talents outside the academic curriculum. Finland places great emphasis on the balance between school learning time and break time. They believe that sufficient breaks are important for recovery and to enhance students' concentration. Therefore, study hours in Finland tend to be shorter compared to other countries. Additionally, they place significant value on extracurricular activities and free time, which helps enhance students' overall well-being.⁶

C. The Habitus of Ciputra School that Implements Positive Learning through Collaboration with Finland

One of the school networks that collaborates with educational agents from Finland is the Citra Kasih School Foundation, Citra Berkat School, and Ciputra Kasih School (SCK SCB), which is under the Ciputra group. Schools in the Ciputra group network develop positive education and adopt character learning curricula from Finland.

Teachers at Citra Kasih School, Citra Berkat School, and Ciputra Kasih School (SCK and SCB) are equipped to create opportunities for success, develop various activities to enhance strengths/advantages, and build situations that increase chances for success. Sincere praise will uplift the spirit of each student and send the message that they are on the right track. There are 3 programs developed and emphasized across SCK SCB as a means of implementing Positive Education as follows:

1. Self Development Challenge (SDC) from Nursery (KB) to Senior High School (SMA) that trains each student to have goals and create planning strategies to achieve their goals.
2. Positive Pals (PPals) is a small community of learners guided by a mentor teacher and conducted regularly to develop the positive character of students.
3. Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM) where each teacher adopts the Finnish Curriculum by developing Positive Education through every learning activity that occurs inside and outside the classroom, focusing on each child's strengths and successes.⁷

D. The Arena of the Relationship Between Ciputra School and Finnish Education Agents

International relations now often involve institutions collaborating, rather than just interactions between countries. Four main factors shape national education policies: liberalization, deregulation, privatization, and stabilization. Economic adjustment refers

⁵ Klingert, L. (2023, February 13). Top five EU countries to educate children. Retrieved from The Brussels Times: <https://www.brusselstimes.com/367176/top-five-eu-countries-to-educate-children>

⁶ Ariasa, K. (2021, Januari 31). Belajar Dari Sistem Pendidikan Finlandia. Retrieved from Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha: <https://undiksha.ac.id/belajar-dari-sistem-pendidikan-finlandia/>

⁷ Author. (2024, 11 25). Positive Education. Retrieved from Sekolah Citrakasih: <https://www.citrakasih.sch.id/positive-education/>

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to making changes that enable national economies to integrate into the global market. As time passes, it becomes increasingly difficult for countries and institutions to avoid participating in the global market.⁸

Thus, at this time, institutions like those in this study are school institutions that are affected by global market trends in conducting business within schools. This is related to the free market, which demands that individuals understand and embody values that apply globally. Through the use of internationally recognized curricula, it is highly likely that graduates will be able to adapt within a global context. Supported by government regulations to enhance national competitiveness, it is necessary to develop International Standard Schools (SBI) at the regency or city level through consistent cooperation between the government and local governments to develop elementary, junior high, senior high schools, and vocational schools that meet international standards. Therefore, Ciputra School can collaborate with the Finnish National Agency for Education to develop education at a global level.

CONCLUSIONS

This research discusses a research design on education from a global perspective, utilizing the social construction approach. The aspect of education in life is one of the most important aspects that helps individuals adapt and interact both locally and globally. The importance of instilling global values has led countries around the world to compete in improving the educational aspects of their nations. Meanwhile, countries with a good reputation, such as Finland, strive to assist developing countries or institutions in enhancing their education. One school in Indonesia that collaborates with Finland is Ciputra School. The school, under the Ciputra Group, implements Positive Learning from Finland in its teaching. Thus, character education at Ciputra School combines the curriculum applicable in Indonesia with the Positive Learning approach from Finland. Thus, why does Ciputra School choose to use Positive Learning from Education Finland as a character development learning? This becomes a research question in this research design. Then, how does Pierre Bourdieu's theory elucidate the factors based on social structure and interactions between Ciputra School and institutional agents in Finland, as explained in Bourdieu's theory? Through qualitative research, including interviews with relevant parties and an examination of documents and data related to the development of Positive Learning at Ciputra School, the findings will be analyzed and organized according to the theoretical framework previously explained.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Through learning in the International Relations Theory class at the University of Indonesia, I have developed the ability to identify appropriate concepts and theories for research in International Relations within the field of education. I have been able to complete an article on education research that is quite complicated because I am still uncertain about which theory to use. Through presentations from the lecturers and my classmates, I was able to identify and apply the right theory for my research, utilizing a social constructionist approach to understand the relationships that address my research questions regarding the application of education and how collaboration between Ciputra school and educational agents from Finland is established. Thank you to the lecturers of the International Relations Theory course and my colleagues who provided feedback on this article.

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